

Deployment of python-based Keylogger Pynput

- 1 **Preparation work in your PC**
 - a) download & install python in Windows and Mac
 - b) for Windows users: turn Microsoft Defender Antivirus real-time protection off temporarily (it would be a false alarm for Pynput)
 - c) for Mac users: open the Privacy pane in System Preferences and add Terminal into *input monitoring*
- 2 **Download Pynput sourcecode from**
<https://github.com/tamaramueller/keylogger>
save it and rename as *keylogger*
move folder *keylogger* into C:\Users\yourPCname\ in windows
into /users/yourPCname/ in macOS
- 3 **Open the Windows Command Prompt (CMD) or Mac OS Terminal. Copy and paste each script line one by one and press *Enter* after each line.**
pip install pynput
py -m pip install keylogger
(win users enter) python C:\Users\yourPCname\keylogger\[keylogger.py](#)
(mac users enter) python3 /users/yourPCname/keylogger/keylogger.py
- 4 **find the logfile.txt in your folder**
C:\Users\yourPCname\ in windows
/users/yourPCname/ in macOS